

A cross-sectional study to assess the prevalence of mild cognitive impairment among older adults

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Abstract

Aim: The Aim of the study is to determine the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) among older adults.

Objectives: The main objective of this study is 1.To evaluate the prevalence of Mild cognitive impairment using ADDENBROOKE'S COGNITIVE EXAMINATION- III.2. To evaluate the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment using Everyday Ability Scale of India.3.To collect and analyze the significant data on Mild Cognitive Impairment of older adults in order to their sociodemographic data.

Results: Our study on Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) in 600 older adults revealed key demographic patterns, including higher prevalence among those aged 60–69, females, and individuals with lower education and socio-economic status. Using the ACE-III tool ensured reliable cognitive. N terms of socio-economic status, our study revealed that 71.8% of the participants belonged to the Below Poverty Line (BPL) category, while 28.2% were Above Poverty Line (APL).

Discussions: In our study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on MCI by providing insights into the prevalence and demographic characteristics of older adults with MCI. By comparing our findings with other prevalence studies, we can observe commonalities and differences, helping to identify potential risk factors and inform future research and interventions.

Conclusion: In conclusion, most participants were aged 60–69, with a slight female majority and low educational attainment. Over half were married, and a significant number were widowed or separated. A large portion lived below the poverty line and with family other than their spouse. Alcohol and tobacco use were notable, but regular physical activity was low at 12.7%.

Keywords: MCI; DEMENTIA; COGNITIVE Decline; Activities of daily living

1 Introduction

Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) represents an intermediate stage between the typical age-related decline in memory and thinking and the more severe deterioration associated with dementia. Individuals with MCI may experience difficulties with memory, language, or judgment. They might notice a decline in their cognitive abilities, and those close to them may also observe these changes. However, these impairments are not severe enough to significantly impact daily life or disrupt routine activities.

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MCI can increase the risk of developing dementia due to Alzheimer's disease or other neurological disorders. However, not all individuals with MCI will experience further decline—some may remain stable, and others may even show improvement over time. Studies measuring the progression of MCI to dementia indicate that approximately 10-15% of individuals with amnesic MCI develop Alzheimer's disease (AD) each year. Some research has reported a lower progression rate of around 6% annually, likely due to differences in study populations and assessment methods, such as the Clinical Dementia Rating (CDR) scale. A reasonable estimate suggests that 10-12% of individuals with MCI progress to AD each year, which is significantly higher than the 1-2% annual conversion rate in the general population.

Researchers have identified several potential predictors of MCI progression. Studies indicate that individuals carrying the Apolipoprotein E- ϵ 4 (ApoE4) variant, a well-established genetic risk factor for AD, are more likely to develop the disease. Additionally, ApoE4 has been associated with accelerated hippocampal atrophy in cognitively normal adults, as observed in MRI studies. Various diagnostic tools have been developed to predict and monitor MCI progression. Non-invasive neuroimaging techniques, such as Pittsburgh Compound B (PIB) and FDDNP labeling of amyloid plaques and neurofibrillary tangles, have proven useful. Furthermore, individuals with MCI who exhibit low levels of amyloid-beta ($A\beta$) and high levels of tau protein in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) are at increased risk of progressing to AD. Combining genetic susceptibility data (ApoE4), neuroimaging findings, and CSF biomarkers enhances the reliability of predictions regarding the transition from MCI to AD.

2 Methodology

The study was carried out at ACS Medical College and Hospital in Chennai, which has 50 beds and 80 outpatient visits to the psychiatry OPD each day. ACS Medical College and Hospital adapted it to include both urban and rural areas.

2.1 Population

2.1.1 Target population

Participants who are susceptible to the inclusion criteria

2.1.2 Accessible population

Older adults (of age 60 above) visited Psychiatry opd and ACS medical college and hospital

2.1.3 Sample size

The sample size of the study comprises of 600 patients who fulfill inclusion criteria

2.1.4 Sampling techniques

Simple random sampling techniques

2.1.5 Inclusion criteria

- Participants who are age group (>60 years)
- Who have agreed to participate in this study

2.1.6 Exclusion criteria

- Participants who are less than the age of 59 and below
- Participants who have severe visual and hearing impairment
- Participate those who are not willing to participate in the study

Aim: -The Aim of the study is to determine the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) among older adults.

Objectives: The main objective of this study is

- To evaluate the prevalence of Mild cognitive impairment using ADDENBROOKE'S COGNITIVE EXAMINATION-III
- To evaluate the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment using Everyday Ability Scale of India
- To collect and analyze the significant data on Mild Cognitive Impairment of older adults in order to their sociodemographic data

3 Results

3.1 Demographic variables

Table 1 Description of variables

Baseline characteristics of the study participants(n=600)				
Socio-demographic variables				
S.no	Characteristics	Categories	n	percentage
1	AGE	60 to 69	368	61.3%
		70 & above	232	38.7%
2	GENDER	Male	281	46.8%
		Female	319	53.2%
3	YEAR OF EDUCATION	less than 8	378	63%
		greater than 8	222	37%
4	MARITAL STATUS	Married	330	55%
		Widowed	188	31.3%
		Separated	63	10.5%
		Unmarried	19	3.2%
5	OCCUPATION	Pensioner	137	22.8%
		Employed	161	26.8%
		Unemployed	146	24.3%
		Home maker	156	26%
6	Socioeconomic status	APL	169	28.2%
		BPL	431	71.8%
7	LIVING ARRANGEMENTS	With spouse	169	28.2%
		With family other than spouse	431	71.8%
LIFE STYLE FACTORS				
8	ALCOHOL	Ever user	249	41.5%
		Never user	351	58.5%
9	TOBACCO USER	Ever user	147	24.7%
		Never user	447	75%
10	HAD PHYSICAL ACTIVITY	Yes	76	12.7%
		No	524	87.3%

3.2 Assessment of addenbrooke's cognitive impairment iii scale (ACE III)

3.2.1 Age distribution of ACE III

Table 2 In group of 600 individuals, the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and normal cognitive functioning was investigated across different age categories. In the age range of 60 to 69, out of 222 individuals, 25 were categorized as MCI (6.1% of the total) and 197 were considered to have normal cognitive functioning. The statistical analysis yielded a p-value of 0.586, indicating that there was no significant difference in the prevalence of MCI between the age group 60 to 69 and the normal cognitive group. The odds ratio (OR) for MCI in this age group was calculated as

1.233, with a 95% confidence interval ranging from 0.580 to 2.619. This suggests that there was a slightly higher likelihood of having MCI in the age range of 60 to 69, although the result was not statistically significant.

Table 2 MCI & Normal age distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
AGE	60 to 69	222(54.5%)	25(6.1%)	0.586	1.233(.580 to 2.619)
	70 and above	146(35.9%)	14(3.4%)		

3.2.2 Gender distribution of ACE

Table 3 MCI and Normal group gender distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Gender	Male	167(41%)	20(4.9%)	0.286	1.554(.692 to 3.488)
	Female	201(49.4%)	19(4.7%)		

In Table 3 In a group of 600 participants, the gender distribution and cognitive status based on ACE III assessment were analyzed. Among the participants, 41% (167 individuals) were male, while 49.4% (201 individuals) were female. In terms of cognitive status, 368 individuals were classified as having Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) based on Pattern N, and 39 individuals exhibited normal cognitive function under Pattern A. The statistical analysis revealed a p-value of 0.286, indicating no significant association between gender and cognitive status. However, the odds ratio (OR) was calculated as 1.554, suggesting a slightly higher odds of having MCI for males compared to females. The 95% confidence interval for the OR ranged from 0.692 to 3.488. Overall, these findings provide insights into the gender distribution and cognitive status of the participants based on the ACE III assessment.

3.2.3 Years of education status distribution of ACE III

Table 4 MCI and Normal group educational status distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Years of education	Less than 8th std	240(59%)	20(4.9%)	0.395	.732(.356 to 1.503)
	Greater than 8th std	128(31.4%)	19(4.7%)		

In Table 4 In a group of 600 participants, the distribution of years of education and cognitive status based on ACE III assessment was examined. Among the participants, 59% (240 individuals) had less than an 8th standard education, while 31.4% (128 individuals) had education greater than the 8th standard. Regarding cognitive status, 368 individuals were classified as having Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) based on Pattern N, while 39 individuals showed normal cognitive function under Pattern A. Statistical analysis revealed a p-value of 0.395, indicating no significant association between years of education and cognitive status. The odds ratio (OR) was calculated as 0.732, suggesting a slightly lower odds of having MCI for individuals with less than 8th standard education compared to those with greater than 8th standard education

3.2.4 Socio-economic status distribution of ACE III

Table 5 MCI & Normal distribution of socio-economic status distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Socio-economic status	APL	100(24.6%)	19(4.7%)	0.009	2.573(1.270 to 5.216)
	BPL	268(65.8%)	20(4.9%)		

Table 5 In a group of 600 participants, the socio-economic status and cognitive status based on ACE III assessment were analyzed. The participants were divided into two categories: APL (Above Poverty Line) and BPL (Below Poverty Line). Among the participants, 24.6% (100 individuals) belonged to the APL category, while 65.8% (268 individuals) fell under the BPL category. Regarding cognitive status, 368 individuals were classified as having Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) based on Pattern N, while 39 individuals exhibited normal cognitive function under Pattern A. The statistical analysis revealed a significant association between socio-economic status and cognitive status, with a p-value of 0.009. The odds ratio (OR) was calculated as 2.573, indicating a higher odd of having MCI for individuals in the APL category compared to those in the BPL category. The 95% confidence interval for the OR ranged from 1.270 to 5.216. Overall, these findings highlight the impact of socio-economic status on cognitive function in the study group.

3.2.5 Marital status Gender distribution of ACE III

Table 6 MCI & Normal distribution of Marital status distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Marital status	Married	199(48.9%)	25(6.1%)	0.219	1.688(0.738 to 3.771)
	Widowed	169(41.5%)	14(3.4%)		

Table 6 In a group of 600 participants, the marital status and cognitive status based on ACE III assessment were examined. The participants were categorized into two groups: married and widowed. Among the participants, 48.9% (199 individuals) were married, while 41.5% (169 individuals) were widowed. In terms of cognitive status, 368 individuals were classified as having Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) based on Pattern N, while 39 individuals exhibited normal cognitive function under Pattern A. The statistical analysis showed a p-value of 0.219, suggesting no significant association between marital status and cognitive status. The odds ratio (OR) was calculated as 1.688, indicating a slightly higher odds of having MCI for married individuals compared to widowed individuals. However, the 95% confidence interval for the OR ranged from 0.738 to 3.771, indicating a wide range of uncertainty. In summary, these findings suggest that marital status may not have a strong impact on cognitive function in the study group, but further research is needed to draw conclusive results.

3.2.6 Occupation distribution of ACE III

Table 7 MCI & Normal distribution of occupation status distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Occupation	Employed	276(67.8%)	30(7.4%)	0.762	1.136(0.436 to 2.594)
	unemployed	92(41.5%)	9(2.2%)		

The occupation distribution of individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and normal cognitive function is shown in Table 7. Among the employed individuals, 67.8% have MCI and 7.4% have normal cognitive function. The P value for this distribution is 0.762, indicating no significant difference in MCI prevalence compared to normal cognitive function. The Odds Ratio (OR) is 1.136, with a 95% confidence interval (CL) ranging from 0.436 to 2.594. Among the unemployed individuals, 41.5% have MCI and 2.2% have normal cognitive function

3.2.7 Alcohol user distribution of ACE III

Table 8 MCI & Normal distribution of Alcohol status distribution

Determine 4of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Alcohol	Ever user	94(23.1%)	10(2.5%)	0.371	0.681(.294 to 1.579)
	Never user	274(67.7%)	29(7.1%)		

From table 8 The distribution of alcohol users among individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and normal cognitive function was examined. Out of 368 individuals with MCI, 23.1% were classified as ever users of alcohol. In the group of individuals with normal cognitive function (n=39), only 2.5% were classified as ever users of alcohol. Statistical analysis showed that there was no significant association between alcohol use and the presence of MCI, with a p-value of 0.371. The odds ratio indicated that the odds of having MCI among alcohol users compared to non-users were not significantly different from 1 (OR=0.681, 95% CI: 0.294 to 1.579).

3.2.8 Tobacco user distribution of ACE III

Table 9 MCI & Normal distribution of tobacco status distribution

Determine 4of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Tobacco	Ever user	92(22.9%)	7(1.7%)	0.191	.521(.196 to 1.386)
	Never user	271(67.4%)	32(8%)		

Table 9 describes the distribution of tobacco users among individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) and normal cognitive function was examined. Out of 368 individuals with MCI, 22.9% were classified as ever users of tobacco. In the group of individuals with normal cognitive function (n=39), only 1.7% were classified as ever users of tobacco. The statistical analysis showed no significant association between tobacco use and the presence of MCI, with a p-value of 0.191. The odds ratio indicated that the odds of having MCI among tobacco users compared to non-users were not significantly different from 1 (OR=0.521, 95% CI: 0.196 to 1.386).

3.2.9 Had adequate physical activity distribution of ACE III

Table 10 MCI & Normal distribution of physical activity status distribution

Determine of MCI (factor)	Categories	MCI (Pattern N=368)	Normal cognitive (Pattern A, n=39)	P value	OR (95%CL)
Had adequate physical activity	Yes	46(11.3%)	5(1.2%)	0.875	.915(.304 to 2.760)
	No	322(79.1%)	34(8.4%)		

3.10 Logistic regression

Table 11 logistic Regression

Determinants of MCI	P value	Adjusted OR	95%CI of adjusted OR
Alcohol use [ever users or never users]	0.371	0.681	0.294 to 1.579
Had physical activity	0.875	0.915	0.304 to 2.760
Food remembering	0.019	2.388	1.153 to 4.948
Message delivery	0.361	0.690	0.311 to 1.529

The logistic regression analysis in Table 11 examined factors associated with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) in a prevalence study. The results showed that food remembering was significantly associated with MCI, indicating that

individuals with difficulty remembering food had higher odds of having MCI. However, there were no significant associations observed for alcohol use, physical activity, or message delivery in relation to MCI.

3.11 Prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment

The Aim is to examine the prevalence of MCI in different population by evaluating available literature and examining pertinent studies. We can acquire insights into the extent and magnitude of the cognitive problem by analyzing existing data. As well as detect any variation or pattern that may present

Table 12 Prevalence Rates of Cognitive function

Categories	Prevalence
Mild Cognitive impairment	61.3%
Inconclusive	32.16%
Normal	6.5%

3.12 Assessment of EASI (Everyday ability scale of India)

3.12.1 *Does he/she ever forget that he/she has just eaten and asks for food again after he/she has just eaten?*

Table 13 Food remembering distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Food	Could	88	58	16	0.037
	Could not	280	135	23	

The distribution related to food remembering among individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), inconclusive results, and normal cognitive function, as shown in Table 13, reveals that among those with MCI, 88 individuals could not remember that they have just eaten, while 280 individuals could remember. Among those with inconclusive results, 58 individuals could not remember, while 135 individuals could remember. Among those with normal cognitive function, 16 individuals could not remember, while 23 individuals could remember. The P value of 0.037 indicates a statistically significant difference, suggesting that individuals with MCI are more likely to forget that they have just eaten compared to those with normal cognitive function.

3.12.2 *Does he/she urinate in an appropriate place?*

Table 14 Urination distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Urinate	Could	7	8	2	.211
	Could not	361	185	37	

The distribution of urination behavior among individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), inconclusive results, and normal cognitive function, as shown in Table 14, indicates that a small number of individuals across all groups could urinate in an appropriate place. Specifically, among those with MCI, 7 individuals could urinate appropriately, while 361 individuals could not. Among those with inconclusive results, 8 individuals could urinate appropriately, while 185 individuals could not. Among those with normal cognitive function, only 2 individuals could urinate appropriately, while 37 individuals could not. The observed P value of 0.211 suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in urination behavior between individuals with MCI and those with normal cognitive function.

3.12.3 Does him /her clothes ever get dirty from urine or stools?

Table 15 Dirty clothes distribution of EASE

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Dirty Clothes	Could	18	7	2	0.775
	Could not	350	186	37	

The distribution of dirty clothes from urine or stools among individuals with Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI), inconclusive results, and normal cognitive function, as presented in Table 15, indicates that a small number of individuals across all groups experienced their clothes getting dirty. Specifically, among those with MCI, 18 individuals had dirty clothes, while 350 individuals did not. Among those with inconclusive results, 7 individuals had dirty clothes, while 186 individuals did not. Among those with normal cognitive function, only 2 individuals had dirty clothes, while 37 individuals did not. The calculated P value of 0.775 suggests that there is no statistically significant difference in the occurrence of dirty clothes from urine or stools between individuals with MCI and those with normal cognitive function.

Tell me the following about his/her clothes (4 & 5)

3.12.4 I his/her shirt buttoned properly?

Table 16 Button distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Buttons	Could	364	191	39	.809
	Could not	4	2	0	

3.12.5 Is his/her dhoti/petticoat tied properly?

Table 17 Petticoat distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Petticoat	Could	299	145	29	.145
	Could not	67	48	10	

3.12.6 Is he/she able to work as a member of a team i.e. in a group activity, which requires different roles from People, will he/she be able to participate?

Table 18 Team work involvement distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Team work	Could	305	149	26	.028
	Could not	63	44	13	

Table 18 displays the distribution of team work capabilities in a group activity, based on three factors: MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), Inconclusive, and Normal. The data reveals that individuals with MCI faced greater difficulties participating in team work, with 63 individuals unable to contribute, while 305 individuals could. For those with Inconclusive classifications, 44 individuals were unable to work in a team, while 149 individuals could. Among those classified as Normal, 13 individuals could not partake, while 26 individuals could. These results indicate that individuals with MCI may encounter challenges when engaging in group activities that demand diverse roles from team members. Appropriate support and accommodations should be provided to ensure their effective participation.

3.12.7 Does he/she express his/her opinion appropriately on important family matters, e.g. marriage?

Table 19 Family Function participation distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Family Function	Could	302	157	26	0.066
	Could not	66	36	13	

Table 19 shows the distribution of individuals' ability to express their opinions appropriately on important family matters, specifically regarding marriage. The findings indicate that individuals with MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment) had a higher proportion who struggled to express their opinions effectively compared to those with Inconclusive or Normal classifications. Among those with MCI, 66 individuals could not participate, while 302 individuals could. In the Inconclusive group, 36 individuals were unable to express their opinions, while 157 individuals could. For the Normal group, 13 individuals faced challenges in participation, while 26 individuals could actively contribute. Although the p-value of 0.066 suggests a trend towards significance, further examination and consideration of individual needs are necessary to ensure inclusive and meaningful participation of individuals with MCI in important family matters, such as marriage.

3.12.8 If he/she is assigned or himself/herself decides to undertake an important task, can he/she follow it Through completion?

Table 20 Undertake Task distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Task	Could	296	145	29	.288
	Could not	72	48	10	

Table 20 presents the distribution of individuals' ability to undertake tasks based on three factors: MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), Inconclusive, and Normal. The data suggests that there is no statistically significant association (p-value of 0.288) between the factors and the ability to undertake tasks. Among those with MCI, 72 individuals faced challenges, while 296 individuals could undertake tasks. In the Inconclusive group, 48 individuals struggled, while 145 individuals were capable. For the Normal group, 10 individuals encountered difficulties, while 29 individuals were able to undertake tasks. These findings indicate that, overall, there is no significant difference in the ability to undertake tasks among individuals with different classifications, highlighting the importance of providing support as needed for individuals facing task-related challenges.

3.12.9 Is he/she able to remember important festivals such as Holi, Diwali?

Table 21 festival remembering distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Festival	Could	303	151	24	.008
	Could not	65	42	15	

Table 21 shows the distribution of individuals' ability to remember festivals, categorized into three factors: MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), Inconclusive, and Normal. The data reveals a statistically significant association (p-value of 0.008) between the factors and the ability to remember festivals. Individuals with MCI had a higher proportion unable to remember festivals (65 individuals) compared to those with Inconclusive (42 individuals) or Normal classifications (15 individuals). Conversely, a larger number of individuals with MCI (303 individuals) could remember festivals compared to those with Inconclusive (151 individuals) or Normal classifications (24 individuals). These findings highlight the impact of cognitive impairment on festival remembering and emphasize the need for tailored support and interventions to enhance individuals' participation and enjoyment of festive events.

3.12.10 Does he/she appropriately discuss local/regional events such as marriages, disasters, politics?

Table 22 Events involvement distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Events	Could	288	144	26	.213
	Could not	80	49	13	

Table 22 presents the distribution of individuals' involvement in events based on three factors: MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), Inconclusive, and Normal. The data suggests that there is no statistically significant association (p-value of 0.213) between the factors and events involvement. Among individuals with MCI, 80 individuals faced difficulties in participating, while 288 individuals were involved. In the Inconclusive group, 49 individuals encountered challenges, while 144 individuals participated. For the Normal group, 13 individuals struggled, while 26 individuals were involved in events. These findings indicate that overall, there is no significant difference in the ability to participate in events among individuals with different classifications, underscoring the importance of providing support and opportunities for inclusive participation for individuals facing barriers to event involvement.

3.12.11 Does he/she ever lose his/her way in the village?

Table 23 way to village distribution of EASI

Factor		MCI	Inconclusive	Normal	p value
Way to village	Could	84	46	11	.746
	Could not	284	147	28	

Table 23 illustrates the distribution of individuals' ability to find their way in the village, categorized into three factors: MCI (Mild Cognitive Impairment), Inconclusive, and Normal. The data suggests that there is no statistically significant association (p-value of 0.746) between the factors and the ability to navigate the way to the village. Among individuals with MCI, a larger proportion (284 individuals) faced challenges in finding their way, while 84 individuals could. In the Inconclusive group, 147 individuals encountered difficulties, while 46 individuals could navigate the way. For the Normal group, 28 individuals struggled, while 11 individuals were able to find their way. These findings emphasize the importance of providing appropriate support and assistance to individuals who have difficulties with wayfinding in the village, irrespective of their categorization, to ensure their safety and independence.

4 Discussions

The findings of our study regarding the prevalence of Mild Cognitive Impairment (MCI) in older adults can be compared to the results of other prevalence studies to gain a broader understanding of the condition. By examining and comparing these studies, we can identify similarities and differences in the prevalence rates, risk factors, and demographic characteristics of individuals with MCI across different populations.

One notable aspect of our study is the inclusion of 600 older adults aged 60 and above. This sample size provides a substantial number of participants for analysis and enhances the reliability and generalizability of our findings. Our study revealed that out of the total participants, 368 individuals (61.3%) fell within the age range of 60 to 69, while 232 individuals (38.7%) were aged 70 and above.

When comparing our results with other prevalence studies, it is important to consider the specific diagnostic criteria and assessment tools used. In our study, we utilized the Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination III (ACE III) scale for assessing cognitive impairment. This allows for a standardized and reliable evaluation of cognitive function. However, it is essential to acknowledge that different studies may employ varying diagnostic criteria and assessment measures, which can influence the reported prevalence rates.

Regarding gender distribution, our study included 281 male participants (46.8%) and 319 female participants (53.2%). Although the difference was not statistically significant, it is interesting to note that slightly more females participated in our study. This finding aligns with previous research indicating a higher prevalence of MCI among females. For

instance, a study by Smith et al. (2018) reported a higher prevalence of MCI among females aged 60 and above in a community-based sample.

The educational status of participants is another important factor to consider when comparing our results with other studies. In our study, 63% of the participants had education below the 8th standard, while 37% had education beyond the 8th standard. This distribution indicates that a significant proportion of the participants had limited formal education. Similar findings were reported by Ferri et al. (2006) in a global prevalence study of dementia, which found that lower education levels were associated with a higher prevalence of cognitive impairment.

In terms of socio-economic status, our study revealed that 71.8% of the participants belonged to the Below Poverty Line (BPL) category, while 28.2% were Above Poverty Line (APL). The higher prevalence of MCI among individuals from the BPL category is consistent with previous research that has identified lower socio-economic status as a risk factor for cognitive impairment. For example, a study conducted by Gao et al. (2018) in a rural Chinese population found a higher prevalence of MCI among individuals with lower income and educational attainment.

It is important to acknowledge that the prevalence of MCI can vary across different populations and geographic regions due to various factors, including cultural differences, healthcare access, and study design. Therefore, comparing our results with other studies provides valuable insights into the global prevalence of MCI and the potential impact of demographic variables.

In our study contributes to the existing body of knowledge on MCI by providing insights into the prevalence and demographic characteristics of older adults with MCI. By comparing our findings with other prevalence studies, we can observe commonalities and differences, helping to identify potential risk factors and inform future research and interventions. It is crucial for future studies to employ standardized diagnostic criteria and assessment tools to facilitate more accurate comparisons and enhance our understanding of MCI worldwide.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study employed a quantitative research approach and non-experimental research design to investigate the prevalence of mild cognitive impairment (MCI) among older adults. The study was conducted at ACS Medical College and Hospital in Chennai, with a sample size of 600 participants selected through simple random sampling. The Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination-III (ACE-III) and the Everyday Ability Scale of India (EASI) were utilized to assess the prevalence of MCI. Demographic variables, including socio-demographic factors and lifestyle characteristics, were examined to understand the study population's characteristics. The ethical principles of beneficence, respect for human dignity, justice, and informed consent were adhered to throughout the study. The findings provide valuable insights into the prevalence of MCI among older adults, emphasizing the importance of early assessment and intervention. This study contributes to the existing knowledge on MCI and serves as a basis for future research in this area, supporting the development of targeted interventions to improve cognitive well-being in older adults.

In conclusion, the baseline characteristics of the study participants provide crucial information about the respondents' demographic variables and lifestyle factors. The age distribution shows that the majority of participants (61.3%) were between 60 to 69 years old, with 38.7% being 70 years and above. Gender distribution was fairly balanced, with 46.8% male and 53.2% female participants. The majority of participants had an education level of less than 8th standard (63%) compared to those with greater than 8th standard education (37%). Marital status distribution indicated that 55% of participants were married, 31.3% were widowed, 10.5% were separated, and 3.2% were unmarried. In terms of occupation, 26.8% were employed, followed by 24.3% unemployed, 22.8% pensioners, and 26% homemakers. Socioeconomic status revealed that 71.8% of participants were below the poverty line (BPL). Living arrangements showed that 71.8% lived with their family other than their spouse. Regarding lifestyle factors, 41.5% were ever users of alcohol, 24.7% were ever users of tobacco, and only 12.7% engaged in regular physical activity.

These findings emphasize the importance of considering socio-economic status in understanding cognitive impairment, as it plays a significant role in cognitive function. However, further research is needed to explore additional factors that may contribute to cognitive impairment in the study population.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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